

Research

“A Cathedral of doom”: Oral tradition and prophecy in Kofi Awoonor’s “The Cathedral” and Kofi Anyidoho’s “The Kingmaker”

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Abstract: Oral tradition, which assembles knowledge, memories, and values have been typically configured in the linguistic artifacts of a nonliterary or aesthetic-literary nature. This is by far reflected in the works of most African literary writers who reappropriate the colonial heritage and language to be the foundation upon which they build their innovation, activism, and the general education of their African brethren. The works of Kofi Awoonor and Kofi Anyidoho fall within this categorization. Some of their works depict them as disquieted individuals advocating for the sustenance of the African tradition. The issues they contend with revolve around those who were encroaching on their territory and oppressing their culture. This they do by immersing their works in their Ghanaian Ewe heritage. It is against this backdrop that the current study attempts to examine Kofi Awoonor’s “The Cathedral”. It stresses the poem as a prophecy to the president, Akuffo-Addo’s pledge to build a national cathedral in Ghana. The study establishes the poem as a part of the blame culture that many Africans have used to explain the situation on the continent. To support the analysis of this poem is Kofi Anyidoho’s “The Kingmaker” which provides a caution to the problem generated by a foreign invasion in the African continent. The study launches the place of the two poems as an immense contribution to modern African poetry by relying on the concept of orality to undertake a content analysis of the two poems. It identifies that the two poems kindle a nationalistic feeling in Africans at large.

Keywords: Advocacy, Africa, oral, poetry, religion, tradition

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Accepted: 20 August, 2023; **Published:** 30 August, 2023

How to cite this article: Josephine Delali Ofei (2023). “A Cathedral of doom”: Oral tradition and prophecy in Kofi Awoonor’s “The Cathedral” and Kofi Anyidoho’s “The Kingmaker”. *North American Academic Research*, 6(8), 10-19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8300133>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

In the words of William Wordsworth, poetry is the spontaneous overflow of powerful feelings arising from emotions recollected in tranquility in the language of the ordinary man(1). Poetry is largely seen as a genre of literature that uses concise but dense words to mean something more than the ordinary language may hold. On this, Brancacci(2) maintains that poetry is the essence of life, its music, its arts; the rhythm of dancing words. Traditionally, a good deal of African life is embedded in poetry. It covers all that ordinary everyday speech does not express. There is poetry in libation, the naming of a child as well as the enstoolment of a king among others. Traditional African poetry involves

an extremely complicated sense of materials and structures. Okon(3) is of the view that modern African poetry embraces some kind of commitment. This commitment accords it with a utilitarian value.

African poetry, just like any other poetry has been used to express various emotions and concerns ranging from childbirth through love to death and hope. It expresses the challenges, peculiarities, and prospects of culture, tradition, politics, and religion in Africa. Traditionally, African politics, religion, and culture seem to be merged. That aside, the current politics in Africa can be traced to the period of colonialism when Africa was formally partitioned into separate territories by colonial masters. This transformation wielded Africa into a large geopolitical unit irrespective of compatibility, historical or cultural ties. After independence, the new political system imposed by the departing colonial masters was handed over to the African political elites. Unfortunately, the new African leaders did not have time to get acquainted with the workings of the foreign system. Consequently, what happened was political disorder, tribal genocide, corruption, civil wars, coups, and political assassinations. Hence, most African writers resorted to literary works, especially poetry to press home this political fabric of the continent with a view of changing the prevailing poor conditions of the masses who suffer neglect at the hands of the ruling elites. To this end, Kofi Anyidoho(4) in *The Pan African Ideal in Literatures of the Black World* refers to Chinweiz et al (1980) thus:

The African orature is important to this enterprise of decolonizing African literature, for the important reason that it is the incontestable reservoir of the values, sensibilities, aesthetics, and achievements of traditional African thought and imagination outside the plastic arts. Thus, it must serve as the ultimate foundation, guidepost, and point of departure for a modern liberated African literature. It is the root from which modern African literature must draw sustenance (p. 30).

Notably, Anyidoho is passionate about creating metaphors and preserving his Ewe heritage. This he blends with “an intellectual keenness and a skill with words” (5, p. 508). This study brings in one of Anyidoho’s poems as a support to Kofi Awoonor’s “The Cathedral”.

Kofi Anyidoho and Kofi Awoonor, are two patriotic Ghanaian poets who continue to demonstrate their commitment to addressing the social and political problems associated with their cultural heritage. They are committed to writing about societal issues as they perceive them and make the effort to shape the social and political landscape of the continent. Both Anyidoho and Awoonor’s poems are largely influenced by the Ewe (one of the major tribes in Ghana and Togo) oral tradition including proverbs and idioms which have come to enrich the English language thus bringing the Ewe heritage to bear in English. This draws our attention to language being at the heart of the decolonizing process of African nations and reinstituting African national identities and cultural heritages. This ideology is in sync with Ngũgĩ Wa Thiong’O’s proposition in his *Decolonising the Mind*(6) that the choice of language and its usage are crucial to a people’s definition of themselves in connection to the entire cosmos. To him, language rather than history or culture is the enabling condition of human consciousness. Arguably, language use either directly enables consciousness or serves as one of the distinguishing characteristics of consciousness. This is what draws a clean line between humans and non-humans. The English language, for years, has served the linguistic oppressive purpose of being the main instrument by which the former British colonizers establish and uphold political control over their territories in Africa as well as the available wealth, and resources present in these areas. On this, Achebe(7) advocates for African writers who use the African version of English to express;

a new voice coming out of Africa, speaking of the African experience in a worldwide language to strive to make good use of the English language in a way that brings out [their] message best without altering the language to the extent that its value as a medium of international exchange will be lost.

[They] should aim at fashioning out an English which is at once universal and able to carry his peculiar experience (p. 27).

For that matter, poets like Awoonor and Anyidoho appropriate the English language that was taught to them to fight back in their quest to hold in high esteem their African heritage. Thus, they inculcate the oral tradition into their literary works.

Notably, before the growing popularity of writing as a form of communication, orality was by far the most frequent in Africa. A society's history, culture, and religious beliefs, among others, are passed down from generation to generation by oral tradition. According to Wilson(8) in African societies, oral tradition is the method through which history, stories, folktales, and religious beliefs are passed on from generation to generation. Orality, in simple terms, may be defined as spoken rather than written. On this, Nogueira(9) intimates that;

oral tradition congregates knowledge, memories, values, and symbols generally configured in linguistic objects of non-literary or aesthetic-literary nature, objects with or without consignment in written testimonies, accomplished vocally and recognizable collectively and during consecutive generations in an anatomy built by the laws of traditionality – anonymity, persistence, variation (p. 164).

This creates the understanding that oral tradition is integral to African culture and way of life. Oral tradition is highly valued in most African civilizations because it is the main way through which culture is transmitted. Additionally, it is a means of communicating attitudes and feelings. Africans have relied on oral tradition for hundreds of years to transmit vital customary values and morals related to living. The mysteries of the universe and the purpose of existence on earth are explained by oral tradition. This is because the majority of African societies did not have a created alphabet for millennia. It may be for this reason that Wilson's(8) citation of the African scholar, Mbiti(10), maintains that the majority of Africans "did not invent an alphabet for reading or writing" (p. 1). As a result, they were unable to preserve written records of their past. Thus, oral transmission of information about customs, culture, traditions, and religion, among other topics, was the accepted method for doing so from one generation to the next. It served as a repository for their first memories and convictions. So, oral traditions contained a large portion of the evidence about the past of the African people. However, Finnegan(11) and Ong(12) earlier emphasized that Africa possesses both written and oral traditions. It is mainly the oral form of communication that has long been useful to Africans and, by extension, the rest of humanity. Hence, Olajubu(13) foregrounds the significance of "orality" further by contending that, in contrast to written forms, oral traditions may and will always persist without writing. This statement is grounded on the fact that in the past, most Africans relied more on verbal communication than the written form, and oral communication was still used to inform people about their origins, ancestry, communal ethics, and taboos among others.

It is from the oral tradition that African oral literature is birthed. Oral literature is the earliest form of literature and may be understood as that aspect of literature that has been kept and passed on by word of mouth rather than in writing. Nandwa and Bukenya(14) earlier defined oral literature as "those utterances, whether spoken, recited or sung whose composition and performances exhibit to an appreciable degree the artistic characteristics of accurate observations, vivid imagination, and ingenious expressions" (p.1). This definition makes us understand that certain strategies may be employed in oral literature but may not necessarily be effective in written forms. Such is the poetry of Kofi Awoonor and Kofi Anyidoho.

Compared to most other poets, the unity and continuity evoked in the works of these two major Ewe poets are, however, of a different order. In the case of Kofi Anyidoho, he waves a new element of allusions to figures and movements of varying geographical and cultural origin, making up a somber meditation on the recent history of a country that brings together the ancient empires of West Africa. His poetry sings not of dreams of secession, but of the life of the Ghanaian nation as a whole: the hopes raised by the various political leaders and their corresponding disappointments. It is worthy of note that the sense of unity pervading both Awoonor and Anyidoh's poems concerns

the cultural and spiritual sphere more directly than the political one. Their poetry is woven into the traditional art of the Ewe poets, using it and the thought on which it is based as a launching pad for new reflections. However, Wilkinson(15) observes that such an approach sheds light upon the nature and purpose of their production. It is therefore not surprising when Ojaide(16) observes; "Kofi Awoonor's poems echo his native Ewe rhythms, and the poet is highly influenced by his researching Ewe dirges and folktales" (p. 308). One poem which typifies this tendency is Kofi Awoonor's "The Cathedral"(17). It is a lamentation of the desecration and destruction of an otherwise authentic African milieu as represented by a tree whose "boughs [are] stretched, across a heaven/ [and] brightened by the last fires of a tribe" (lines 4 - 5). However, with the advent of colonialism, "surveyors and builders" (line 6) are sent to cut it down and in its place "A huge senseless cathedral of doom is built" (line 9).

While he shows a deep interest in the oral tradition of African poetry, Awoonor has also enriched his work through his understanding of Western literature. For instance, Senanu and Vincent(17) observe that excerpts from Dante form an important motif in "This Earth, My Brother", and many of the poems in Awoonor's *The Promise of Hope: New and Selected Poems*(18) owe something to English writers from Shakespeare through T. S. Eliot. Awoonor has himself remarked on the convergence in his work of Ewe oral tradition and the English language thus:

I have always felt, perhaps involuntarily, I should take my poetic sensibility if you like the word, from the tradition that sort of feeds my language, because in my language there is a lot of poetry, there is a lot of music and there is a lot of literary art, even though not written, and so I take my cue from this old tradition, and begin to break it into English, to give it a new dimension as it were (19), p. 716).

Awoonor's poetry is exciting because it offers (at its best) the creative fusion of two cultures. His poetry is also exciting because it transcends particular cultures. The structure of many of Awoonor's poems resembles certain features of African traditional oral verse. Images, phrases, and even whole stanzas in his poems of the early sixties are repeated in later works, especially in the two long poems which mark the main stages of his development. Awoonor's poetry often achieves the illusion of this kind of spontaneity and a logical movement; in fact, it is usually intellectually coherent, having a sophisticated unity of symbol and theme. One such theme has to do with Christianity and its influence in Africa and this is expressed in his poem "The Cathedral" which forms the basis of this study. However, before discussing this poem, it is necessary to touch on the poetic commitment of Anyidoho, whose poem is partly analyzed in support of Awoonor's "The Cathedral".

Kofi Anyidoho is another renowned Ghanaian poet and cultural activist who is noted for his ability to maintain a distinctly African voice in his poems. His poetry which is heavily impacted by the Ewe customs and culture has as its major themes; public, political, and social concerns. He is categorized as a member of the second generation of modern Ghanaian poets whose poetry is intended to be chanted or sung. Okon(3) classifies Anyidoho under "Ghana's new generation of poets" (p. 21). This group of poets is identified by their "masses-oriented poetry" (Ibid, p. 21). Their poetry is implied to be dedicated to the ultimate emancipation of the masses from the chains of political and economic enslavement. That is to say that Anyidoho is a revolutionary of sorts. Due to his profound awareness of the class conflicts in Africa as the driving force behind African history, Anyidoho creates committed literature. He refuses to step down in the face of corruption because he believes that the working classes remain the only hope for the continent.

Another major aspect of Anyidoho's poetry is the concept of unity and continuity which is grounded in the Ewe tradition. This concept is evoked in his poetry through the image of new elements which he weaves into the old. These elements make up a dismal reflection on the recent history of a nation that unites numerous peoples under the banner of one of the historic empires of West Africa by making references to personalities and movements of various geographical and cultural origins. The old transitioning into the new is reflected in how he inculcates the oral tradition into written poetry. However, Anyidoho's perspective on tradition suggests that it is improper to use the transition from oral to written tradition as a significant indicator of growth since it does not account for the separation of the past

from the present. For him, the past and present are intertwined. Insofar as the essence of traditional African poetic forms is recreated in the framework of poetic performances, Anyidoho finds it unnecessary to artificially divide the past from the present. And so, through the poem "The Kingmaker", Anyidoho(20) seems to be cautioning his audience to be weary of the foreign influx that seems to be overshadowing the African traditional way of life. This will be further elaborated upon in the analysis of this paper.

Observably, most literary studies on Anyidoho's "The Kingmaker" and Awoonor's "The Cathedral" focus on themes and in some cases, the complexity of the styles of the individual poems. However, with the commencement of the efforts by the current president of Ghana, His Excellency Nana Addo Danquah Akuffo-Addo, to fulfill his pledge of building a national cathedral, there has been a national debate where most people gave a popular interpretation of Awoonor's "The Cathedral" as a prophecy of what was to ensue during the building of this cathedral. The current study takes a cue from this discursive trend and goes further by bringing in Anyidoho's "The Kingmaker" as an awakening call to the invasion of a foreign rule.

Analysis and Discussion

Poetry often contains explicit and implicit emotive generalizations about life. It is a mere reflection of the state of mind of the poet. Thus, the words used by a poet will in most cases come out of the depth of what they feel at the time of writing. Although at the time Awoonor and Anyidoho were writing their poetry, the case of Ghana's national cathedral was yet to be conceived. These poems were mainly written to address some pressing issues of the time but since 2018, after Nana Addo Danquah Akuffo-Addo made known his promise to God to build a national cathedral, most people have reappropriated Awoonor's poem to be a prophesy of what was to transpire after this Ghanaian president made that pledge. This section of the study presents a discussion of "The Cathedral" to that effect. This is followed by an analysis of the section of "The Kingmaker" which supports "The Cathedral" by serving as a wake-up call to oppression and foreign influx.

Many Ghanaians have turned to Kofi Awoonor's poetry, "The Cathedral", as a source of inspiration to strengthen their stance in light of the vitriolic opposition to the construction of the national cathedral in Ghana. The poem has some merit in the sense that, the setting is an African land. And prior to the arrival of the Westerners, Africans had a tradition that was merged with their religious beliefs. This made it easier for religion to be used by the West as one of the main tools by which Africa was ruled. Awoonor in this poem emphasizes his allegiance to his African traditional religious belief. He belongs to the Afrikania Mission, a neo-traditional organization. Afrikania Mission was established in Ghana in 1982 by a former Catholic Priest, Kwabena Damuah, who resigned from the church and assumed the traditional priesthood title, Osofo Okomfo (21). It is a traditional revivalist organization that is committed to making Christianity unpopular, thereby, foregrounding the ancestral traditional beliefs. As an ardent member of this ministry, Awoonor wrote "The Cathedral" as part of his unwavering hostility towards Christianity. He was one of the numerous nationalist academics who set out to rewrite, reconstruct, deconstruct, and refute the epistemic injustice they believed Europeans had committed against Africa. He wrote his poem in an attempt to legitimize and canonize his African ideology in a skilled criticism. Reading the poem from an Afrocentric perspective, one is likely to conclude that it is an ingredient for a Ghanaian nationalistic feeling.

That aside, "The Cathedral" is also a part of the blame culture that many Africans have used to explain the situation on the continent. The cathedral is the main symbol of the Christian religion in this poem. And how it is used implies that it was one of the underlying pretexts that the Europeans used to oppress and exploit the various African nations. Ellis and Ter Haar(22) are of the view that religious ideas and the traditional African way of life are intertwined. Africans believe that every aspect of their lives is controlled by a Supreme being who is represented by sub-gods with whom the people can have direct contact of sorts. This means that religion can greatly stimulate an African man's thinking and behavior, hence, it becomes the focal point of their daily activities and decisions. On this, Mbiti(10) makes

us understand that the African man is inherently religious. And so, it is not surprising that the colonizer saw religion as a convenient tool to manipulate Africa. This does not mean that slavery and colonialism had no profound influence on Africa and Africans in general.

What Awoonor seems to be emphasizing is that excessive focus on the negative impacts of colonialism and the externalization of the region's failure has offered Africa a way to avoid acknowledging their involvement in the problems of the continent. It must be pointed out that Africa was not the only continent that had been colonized; Asia and Europe had their fair share of colonialism. However, instead of adopting a positive behavior towards development, most Africans seem to continue the blaming culture, failing to bring about the growth we so desire. It seems most parts of Africa keep repeating the same leadership mistakes than making self-development a priority. Kofi Awoonor specifically criticizes this blaming culture in his poem thus:

They sent surveyors and builders
who cut that tree (lines 6-7)

The use of the pronoun "They" in the Ghanaian traditional context signifies an unspecified group of people, usually superiors whose name the speaker may not want to mention but is quite obvious. However, history also has it that it was through the indigenes that the foreigners had access to the local lands. Kofi Awoonor's poem, "The Cathedral", expresses in a compact and persuasive way the disapproval of a change from the serene and natural life of Africa's past which is symbolized by the "tree" that shed "incense on the infant corn" (lines 3 & 4) to more modern and foreign practices. These practices are foregrounded by his use of the words "surveyors and builders" (line 3). "The Cathedral" is taken to symbolize not only foreign practices which may seem alien to the Africans but also other changes that accompany the interruption of spiritual and commonly shared experiences of the African people or society. A tree in the traditional Ghanaian context is symbolic of growth, prosperity, and a connection between the living and their ancestors. The people of Ghana consider some specific trees as sacred. These sacred trees, which are mostly positioned strategically, have the power to protect the people in the communities in which they are found. For instance, there is the *Mpeni Kofi* tree located in Akuapem Akropong(23). This tree is believed to have been in existence for over three hundred years. It is considered sacred because the people of this community believe it has the power of transforming into a human being at night to guard them against all evil. Hence, cutting such a tree spells "doom" (line 9) for this community.

It must be pointed out that Ghana, before and immediately after independence, was more of a secular state than a Christian one. And so, the comprehensive plan to disparage Christianity includes Kofi Awoonor's outbursts. Understandably, people turned to Awoonor's poem for solace in their rush to criticize the building of a national cathedral. The Ghanaian president's pledge to construct a national Cathedral could be alluded to the Biblical David's pledge to build a temple where the people of God could meet and worship him. While Akuffo-Addo promises to construct a national cathedral, he looks up to the Ghanaian Christians to keep his promise to God. The poet is unarguably unimpressed by the drastic change from the traditional African way of life to a foreign way of doing things. He opens his poem with the following lines:

On this dirty patch
A tree once stood (lines 1& 2).

The poet talks about the benefits of this tree to the indigenes as "shedding incense on the infant corn" (line 3). This particular line indicates innocence where "infant" is concerned and also a sense of abundance. So the great tree of tradition was being protective of the indigenes with "its boughs stretched across heaven" (line 4). This stretch implies a connection between the community and the supreme being who lives in heaven thus, championing the course of an existing African traditional religion. The persona spells out some indication of hope for the future. However, this hope "brightened by the last fires of a tribe" (line 5) was thwarted by the surveyors and builders who were sent to:

... cut that tree

Planting in its place

A huge senseless cathedral of doom (lines 7-9).

The persona is obviously unenthused by the cutting down of the traditional life and the meaningful spirit of the African which is symbolized by the "tree". His expression of bitter emotions over the new religion being planted in Africa is seen in the first line of the poem that reads "On this dirty patch" which is used to describe the land that now holds the "huge senseless cathedral of doom" (line 9). This holy land is dirty because it has been polluted by the imposition of a religion and a governance alien to Africa.

This tree is also symbolic of the tree that was cut down and the sacred rock that was quarried by Azambuja and his Portuguese entourage to build the first castle on the Coast of Guinea in Elmina, Ghana. The quarrying of the rock lays more emphasis on the interference in the natural order of the African life brought about by the construction. The king of that community who is mostly referred to as "Camaianca others render the name as Caramansa or Kwamena Ansa" is said to have strongly opposed the building of the castle (which came along with a church above the dungeons) (24), p. 354). Unfortunately, this first European settlement on the African coast was established in defiance of the native African's request.

Although this poem may seem to protest a foreign religion, it holds a double valency in the sense that it particularly serves as a clear prophecy of what the new religion had in store for the African continent. Awoonor, here, can be described as a true prophet who could see clearly into the future and foretell the proposed building of the national cathedral by the Akuffo-Addo government. It is just about fair that the poet sees this project as a "senseless cathedral of doom" (line 9) carpeted by the dirty patch because as he predicted, the commencement of the project was going to bring about lots of controversy in the nation, particularly, considering the proposed site. According to the Ghanaian media, this is intended to take some major land in Accra, the capital city of Ghana. Particularly, the part that stretches alongside the Osu Cemetery, taking over the land holding the Ridge roundabout, the Scholarship Secretariat, the Passport Office, and the residence of nine judges. In this sense, the tree talked about is symbolic of the judges' residence as well as all the other affected areas. This demolishing decision draws our attention to Oguntola-Laguda's(25) intimation that political leaders manipulate their religious allegiance which is used as a vehicle to achieve their aim.

His Excellency Nana Addo Dankwa Akuffo-Addo's pledge to build a national cathedral is a clear allusion to the story of the Biblical Jephthah in Judges 11 when he promised to give the first thing or person that came out to meet him as a burnt offering to the Lord after he won the battle. Though a difficult task, he was able to fulfill it. Similarly, since a promise to the Lord must be fulfilled, His Excellency Akuffo-Addo is obliged to build this Cathedral. However, unlike the Biblical Solomon who was chosen by God to build the temple his father David had promised God, Nana Akuffo-Addo mostly relies on the Ghanaian Christians to help him fulfill his promise. Unfortunately, contrary to expectations, the plan to build a national cathedral alone generated the basis for a debate between the political and religious elites in Ghana. The idea behind the putting up of a national cathedral by a political figure includes bridging the gap among religion, politics, and tradition. In support of the building of a national cathedral, Skalník (26) argues;

Religion and politics are today, as they were in the past, intertwined so that if they do not form an inseparable couple then they are simply a unity which only the analytic eye of the scholar can distinguish. However, there are social processes underway which indicates that the possibilities exist for a society of citizens who do not need to divinize either the state or anyone else, at least not for public purposes. That religion deserves respect is undeniable, especially when it caters to individuals' balance of personality or those social needs that rationalism cannot fulfill (p. 229).

However, critics are of the view that the reaction the building of a national cathedral has provoked shows a strong skepticism towards such a tendency among Ghanaians. Line 5 of "The Cathedral" actually invites some sort of doom and incantation when the persona clearly observes; "the last fires of a tribe", which could have been the last meal of the physical existence or the last sacrifice to the spiritual gods, symbolizing an end to life or religion of the African

people. At this point, the poet expresses a loss of hope and the welcoming of a new fate which is seemingly senseless and dead compared to their religion. This in a way signifies that Africans had no hope in the newly implemented religion. Awoonor uses this poem to show that the religion of the Africans means life to them whereas the imposition of the Western culture or religion stands for the dead. Awoonor through the use of imagery makes us understand that no wisdom will justify the imposition of a new religion in the place or environment where the former one freely grew. In a larger sphere, the cathedral symbolizes not only the change in religious and spiritual experience but also the purity of local fellowship (life), and freedom which was stolen by the imposition of the colonial government who brought their religion by building the cathedral, a symbol of imperialist and colonial oppression recognized as "huge and senseless". And so, in support of Awoonor, Anyidoho draws his audience's attention to the foreign invasion by observing that:

From across the skyline came the voice
that chained our thunder to the clouds (lines 1&2).

This sounds more like an alien who prevents the success of the indigenes from coming to bear. It has a direct link to the Cathedral as the alien that came "from across the skyline". Anyidoho's poem thus has a bearing on colonialism. Ogunbado(27) defines colonialism as the exploitation by a stronger country of a weaker one or the use of the weaker country's resources to strengthen and enrich the stronger country. The thunder in this case symbolizes the weaker country and the voice, the stronger country.

The persona of this poem rather creates an image of a voice being more powerful to the extent that it "chained our thunder to the clouds". And so, the persona adds:

I will roost among your murmurs
and watch the Kingmakers
making destoolment logic
against the stool they made
only a little while ago. (lines 3-7).

The persona goes on to caution Africans to be careful and not allow themselves to be duped by any foreign person who would give them an arm instead of a thigh. Moreover, he cautions the people to beware of the dangerous "lame Panther" who "plays at Marbles with the Duiker's child" who instead of staying far from danger "insists on revision of the rules" so that the child will not be hurt by its paws (lines 10- 12). However, the persona still observes:

Sodema, there is a rambling in the air
Call the priest to read this blank in our stare. (lines 17&18).

The mention of a priest in line 18 seems to re-establish the old African traditional religious beliefs that Awoonor stresses in his poem. The poet re-establishes the relevance of the traditional priest as the mediator between the adherents and the gods. He has the power to interpret the conditions the people are in, hence, the call for him to "read" the "blank in [their] stare" (line 18).

Conclusion

This study has investigated Awoonor's "The Cathedral" as an imposition of change from the African traditional life and religion to a more complex and foreign way of life that does not correspond to what the African man originally knows. The study revealed that Anyidoho wrote his poem in an attempt to legitimize and canonize his African ideology in a skilled criticism. Hence, an Afrocentric reading of the poem invites the understanding that "The Cathedral" ignites a nationalistic feeling in both Ghanaians and Africans at large. Additionally, the poem is interpreted to foreground the blame culture that many Africans have used to explain the current developmental situation of the continent. It was realized that although this poem may seem to protest a foreign religion, it holds a double valency in the sense that it particularly serves as a clear prophecy of what the new religion had in store for the African continent. The analysis was further supported with an examination of Anyidoho's poem, "The Kingmaker". "The Kingmaker" comes in to

admonish the indigenes to be weary of any foreign invasion. Hopefully, the effort of this study will be rewarding if the findings provide the impetus for further studies on poetry and issues in African literary texts.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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